

KNOWLEDGE AND FREQUENCY OF PLAYING TRADITIONAL FILIPINO GAMES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 17

Issue 6

Pages: 625-630

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1593

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10776451

Manuscript Accepted: 01-25-2024

Knowledge and Frequency of Playing Traditional Filipino Games

Marisol E. Coyoca,* Mary Nicolette D. Sulague, Paolo Javier Requilme, Jann Bryle T. Unajan,
Rafunzel Y. Bulilawa, Edsel Barnette S. Tatad
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Traditional Filipino games are popular among children in all communities, especially millennials. These games demonstrate how resourceful and innovative Filipinos are in creating these games. Being knowledgeable in the selected Filipino traditional games can help in getting a good performance, whereas those who do not have any idea struggle to perform those games. This prompted the study to determine the knowledge and frequency of playing the traditional Filipino games of third-year regular and irregular BPED students. The researchers utilized the descriptive quantitative design. The findings revealed that BPED students were knowledgeable on the selected traditional Filipino games. Among the three elements of the game, the mechanics garnered the highest scores than the history and equipment. In the frequency of playing the selected Traditional Filipino Games, the Patintero game is always played by respondents. Lastly, there is no significant relationship between the students' knowledge and the frequency of playing the selected traditional Filipino game. Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that there is no significant relationship between knowledge and the frequency of playing traditional Filipino games. Even if students are familiar with the games, this does not guarantee that they will play them more frequently.

Keywords: *knowledge, frequency, traditional filipino games*

Introduction

One of the challenges of the BPED students is the lack of knowledge, skills, and experience resulting in poor performance in Traditional Filipino Games. If a teacher asks the students if they know a specific traditional game, they may be familiar with the game's name, but when asked to perform, they would have difficulty performing it, thus resulting in poor performance.

The concept of traditional games is gradually diminishing in today's youth. It is because of the digital age in which we live. Almost everyone owns a device, and even children are capable of using them. Gaming on mobile devices or personal computers is growing more popular among children, particularly among the younger generation, than traditional Filipino games. Computer games like Defense of the Ancients (DOTA), Clash of Clans, Counter-Strike, Rules of Survival, Mobile Legends: Bang-Bang, and others are popular among young people (Aguado, 2013).

Researchers have also found that many journalists and authors engaged in this topic believe that children nowadays do not know how to play traditional Filipino games, leading Congress to submit a House Bill to conserve Philippine Indigenous Games. It entails including it in the proper curriculum for the primary education system in schools, sustaining such games through documentation or other helpful methods, and regularly showcasing such games at national gatherings and appropriate educational events (De La Cruz, 2018). Due to globalization, which frequently leads to a deterioration of cultural and traditional identity, it is a fact that the younger generation is far more educated about international games than Filipino traditional games.

This study allows the researchers to determine whether students are aware of traditional games and how frequently they play the selected traditional Filipino games to know if there is a significant relationship between the two variables. Despite technological advancements that diminish the idea of traditional Filipino games to today's generation, and despite being part of the curriculum at the tertiary level, specifically in physical education, traditional Filipino games are not as familiar to other students enrolled in the said course. The findings of this study may serve as an additional source of information for the PE teachers and the learners, for this had physically and intellectually benefits students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the knowledge and frequency of playing the traditional Filipino games of third-year regular and irregular BPED students. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the knowledge of the third-year BPED students in traditional Filipino games in terms of:
 - 1.1 history of the game;
 - 1.2 mechanics of the game; and
 - 1.3 equipment to be used?
2. What is the frequency of the BPED students playing traditional Filipino games?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the knowledge and frequency of playing traditional Filipino games?

Literature Review

This research is anchored on the expanded awareness model and the learning curve theory, which serves as a pillar in this study.

Expanded Awareness Model relies on the ideas of metacognition and awareness and depicts the connection between both concepts as a dynamic process. This model makes a distinction between knowledge and awareness that is engaged while doing a task (also known as online awareness) and knowledge and awareness that is pre-existing or stored in long-term memory (Cho, 2000). One of the interconnected components of the Expanded Awareness Model is specific knowledge. The knowledge of specific aspects based on the study deals with students' learning the fundamentals of traditional Filipino games. The level of knowledge indicates how well students comprehend the game. It is based on the information presented, such as the game's history, mechanics, and equipment to be utilized, which is one of the factors that relate to the study.

Learning Curve Theory according to Ebbinghaus as cited by Valamis (2022), the foundation of learning curve theory is the idea that an individual becomes more proficient in a task or activity as they constantly do it. This results in less input costs and higher overall output. The Learning Curve Theory is used to monitor, model, and predict the performance of the students and their progress through time. When students play the traditional Filipino game even though they do not have much knowledge of the game, they become skilled or proficient in how the game is played. They will become more versed in the history, mechanics, and equipment of the game.

Games are well known to have a significant influence on a child's learning process, as stated by UNESCO. It is well recognized that playing games benefits children's physical and mental health as well as their education. As a result, "the majority of traditional activities and games, representations of native cultures and ways of life, which contribute to humanity's shared identity, have already disappeared. Due to the combined results of globalization and harmonization of the rich diversity of world athletic history, those that are left are in danger of being extinct (Thesis Blog of Team 13, 2013).

Traditional games are an important element of our cultural and national history. They are cultural and traditional activities that are passed down from generation to generation, involving diverse movements and cognitive games that are meant to educate, socialize, exchange experiences, and impact the development of the young generation. These games are significant since they will eventually implant in children a sense of nationalism and become an integral part of their childhood. People construct traditional games that symbolize the habits, culture, and customs of a country, area, or even a town or village. There are a variety of traditional games. They could be movement games, cognitive games, games with music or dance, word games, and so on. They are primarily passed down through family members and are rarely incorporated as part of the tradition in school curricula (Popeska and Mitkovska, 2017).

Related Studies

Asuncion (2019) discovered that even with access to online games, participants continue to engage in traditional Filipino games. This indicates a narrow gap that, if not addressed in the near future, could become a cause for concern. According to Buan et al. (2010), a significant majority of respondents who continue to play traditional Filipino games express a consensus that they are vastly superior to contemporary games. Additionally, they acknowledge the intrinsic value and relevance of these traditional games, recognizing them as essential components of the unique Filipino history. The results of Rikers and Schmidt's (2009) study also highlight the fact that the use of traditional national games (Larong-Lahi) in the teaching and learning of pre-service physics students created the right conditions and conceptual ecology for them to experience conceptual change and achieve a conceptual understanding of the games. Through their educational experiences, students gradually develop their conceptions of knowledge and learning.

Another study stated that the majority of the respondents agree that the chosen traditional Filipino games of the study are overall motivating, and during the play, they had the opportunity to get involved with failure and success, learning through trial and error. This will not only increase knowledge but will also improve mutual respect and tolerance. This is a concerning outcome that can be related to the fact that the introduction of computer games gradually overshadows indigenous games (Noor et al., 2019). The preceding discussions have unequivocally emphasized the significance of acquiring the skills to play traditional Filipino games. Engaging in these activities not only brings about physical, social, and mental benefits but also fosters a sense of nationalism and cultivates positive values in our interactions with others.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive quantitative design to ascertain participants' knowledge and frequency of playing Traditional Filipino games. The quantitative method is used in order to discover the relationships among these variables.

Participants

The study involved third-year BPED students from Holy Name University during the 2022-2023 academic year. To gather participants, the researchers sent out a letter with information about the study and a consent form to the entire population. The students had the choice to decide if they wanted to join the study or not. Students who responded and gave their consent were included. Inclusion criteria include the following:

1. The student is currently enrolled at HNU (AY 2022-2023).
2. The student must have engaged in online learning over the preceding two semesters
3. (AY 2021-2022).
4. The student uses an asynchronous online platform as a mode of instruction.
5. The student must have completed the course PEED 109 or the Philippine Traditional Games and Sports.

The names of the participants were meticulously safeguarded to ensure complete anonymity. In cases where participants chose not to respond to the questions, replacements are selected according to the specified inclusion criteria.

Instruments

The researchers used a researcher-made questionnaire in a multiple-choice format. The items from the questionnaire were based on the gathered game literature of the Philippine Traditional Games and were formulated in a way that the knowledge and frequency of playing the traditional Filipino games could come out clear. The questionnaire has three parts, namely: the knowledge which was composed of the History, Mechanics, and Equipment to be used in the game; a yes or no section which will determine if the students' play the selected traditional Filipino game; and the students' frequency of playing the traditional Filipino games. A draft of the instrument was shown to the experts for content validation, and the final draft undergo pilot testing in order to establish validity and reliability.

Procedure

Before making the questionnaire and gathering data, the researchers conducted a literature search on the selected traditional Filipino games since the questions are based on the literature. After drafting the literature and questionnaire, the researchers processed the form for the ERB to ensure that the study followed all protocols. A letter was sent to the Dean of the College of Education at Holy Name University requesting permission to conduct the study for third-year BPED students for S.Y. 2022-2023.

Respondents were informed about the nature of their participation as well as the confidentiality of all data gathered throughout the study. A copy of the questionnaire and consent form were sent via email. Respondents used their email addresses to access the form. Once the respondents submitted the form, their responses were automatically collected. The data collected in this study was properly disposed of upon its completion. Following data collection with the help of the statistician, the data were analyzed and tabulated using mean, percentage, and regression analysis.

Ethical Considerations

The respondents were assured that their privacy and identity were protected and the data collected would be treated with the utmost confidentiality and respect. Respondents were also assured that this activity would not expose them to any vulnerabilities or risks.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the study's research questions. To determine the respondents' knowledge and frequency of playing traditional Filipino games and find out whether there is a significant relationship between knowledge and frequency of playing these games, percentage and regression analysis was utilized.

Table 1. Knowledge of BPED students in the Traditional Filipino Games

Level of Knowledge of the Elements of Games	Score/Description	Frequency	Percentage
History	8 – 9 (Excellent)	3	10%
	6 – 7 (Very Good)	7	23%
	4 – 5 (Good)	16	53%
	2 – 3 (Fair)	3	10%
	0 – 1 (Failed)	1	3%
Mechanics	21 – 23 (Excellent)	0	0%
	17 – 20 (Very Good)	5	17%
	12 – 16 (Good)	17	57%
Equipment	6 – 11 (Fair)	8	27%
	0 – 5 (Failed)	0	0%
	3 (Excellent)	13	43%
	2 (Good)	12	40%
	0 – 1 (Failed)	5	17%

Table 1 shows the Knowledge of the third-year BPED students in traditional Filipino games which is divided into three categories: History, Mechanics, and Equipment.

In terms of History, the result shows that 16 respondents garnered a score of 4-5 or 53% on the history of the selected Filipino games with a description of "Good". This means that the students are familiar on the history of the selected traditional Filipino games. The students know how, when, and where, the selected games originated.

In terms of Mechanics, the result shows that 17 respondents garnered a score of 12-16 or 57% on the mechanics of the selected Filipino games with a description of “Good”. This indicates that the students are familiar on the mechanics of the selected traditional Filipino games. The students knows the rules and the process of playing the games.

Lastly, in terms of the Equipment, the result shows that 13 respondents garnered a score of 3 or 43% on the equipment of the selected Filipino games with a description of “Excellent”. The result shows that the students are very well informed on what equipment to be used and how to properly manipulate it in the process of playing the games.

Overall, the students level of knowledge of the elements of games in terms of mechanics is high than history and equipment. Typically in playing games, the rules and the process of the games are the important things the players ask first before participating the games. This is reinforced by the findings of Rikers and Schmidt's (2009) study, which found that students' conceptions of learning and knowledge grow gradually as a result of their educational experiences.

The results of Rikers and Schmidt's (2009) study highlight the fact that the use of traditional national games (Larong-Lahi) in the teaching and learning of pre-service physics students created the right conditions and conceptual ecology for them to experience conceptual change and achieve conceptual understanding of the games.

Table 2. Frequency of the third-year BPED students in playing the selected Traditional Filipino Games

Games	4 (Always)	3 (Sometimes)	2 (Rarely)	1 (Never)	Total
1. Kadang-kadang	2	5	17	6	30
2. Luksong Baka	2	13	15	0	30
3. Luksong Tinik	3	9	17	1	30
4. Patintero	8	9	12	1	30
5. Shato	2	7	18	3	30
6. Sipa Takyang	3	10	17	0	30

Table 2 shows the frequency of the third-year BPED students in playing the selected Traditional Filipino Games. Based on the result, the Patintero game ranked first with 8 respondents who always play the Traditional Filipino Game. Meanwhile, Luksong tinik and Sipa Takyang ranked second with three respondents who always play the Traditional Filipino Game. Lastly, Kadang-kadang is the least played game with 6 respondents who have never played the game followed by Shato. This implies that the respondents preferred playing games that does not need much equipment to play the game. Overall, students still played some of the traditional games not only during their class hour but also during their free time in preparation for the Task practicum.

This is supported in the study by Buan et al. (2010), which found that the majority of respondents who still play the games concur that they are much better compared to modern games by a wide margin. They also recognized the value and relevance of the games and acknowledged that they are an important component of the distinctive Filipino history. In addition, the study of Asuncion (2019), revealed that the research participants still play traditional Filipino games; however, all respondents in the current study provided an even greater percentage (100%), supporting Prestoza et al. (2020) claim that traditional Filipino games continues to be played by children in spite of their accessibility to modern technologies. Prestoza et al. (2020) further elaborated that the elementary school teachers usually observe that some of these Laro ng Lahi are still played by pupils: Tumbang Preso, Sipa, Patintero, Luksong Tinik, Luksong Baka, and Siyato.

Table 3. Significant relationship between the knowledge and frequency of playing traditional Filipino games

	Mean	Std. Deviation	R-value	Interpretation	P-value	Decision
Score	21.3000	4.74995	0.178	Negligible Correlation (Not Significant)	0.346	Accept Ho
Frequency	15.1667	3.60156				

Table 3 presents the significant relationship between the knowledge and frequency of playing traditional Filipino games. The findings revealed that there is no statistically significant relationship between respondents' knowledge and frequency of playing the traditional game. It means that the frequency of playing the traditional games does not rely on whether students have the knowledge of the game. It was shown on tables 1 and 2 that even if majority got high scores it doesn't guarantee that they've always play the game. The higher frequency of playing might depend on the number of times the PE teacher introduces the game to the class or if there is a scheduled practicum of a certain Traditional game. This supported the Expanded Awareness Model, in which respondents' knowledge is based on prior knowledge and has no bearing on how frequently they play the game. It is the initiative of the student to practice the skills needed for the game which increases the frequency of playing the game.

Furthermore, this is supported by the Learning Curve Theory wherein students improve in a task or activity the more they consistently do it. So when students repeatedly play the traditional Filipino games, they become more proficient at it. The more they play the games, they become better at it over time. It is also mentioned in the theory that the relationship of the amount of time spent learning and practicing a skill and the students' overall performance is not linear over time. It can fade or lose over time when little to no effort is put forth to keep it.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the researchers concluded no significant relationship exists between knowledge and the frequency of playing traditional Filipino games. Even if students are familiar with the games, this does not guarantee they will play them more frequently. Students may prioritize other recreational activities due to various factors such as time constraints and personal preferences. Most of the respondents know the game, specifically its mechanics, and they prefer knowing the rules before participating in the games. Understanding the mechanics of traditional Filipino games reflects a preference among respondents for a clear set of rules, suggesting a desire for structured play. Furthermore, Patintero is the most popular game played, which indicates that it is more accessible and simpler to play than the other games. Research findings recommend that students play traditional Filipino games, specifically participating in school and community-related activities. Teachers incorporate traditional Filipino games in classroom activities. Also, organize activities that involve traditional Filipino games as a way of preserving our culture.

References

- Aguado, D. (2013). *The Traditional Filipino Street Games are Alive in the Philippines*. Magna Kultura Foundation: A Philippines Arts and Culture Organization. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/4d5ydd8k>
- Agustin, M. L. P. (2020). Proposed Unification of Indigenous Games in Teaching Physical Education in Cagayan National High School, the Philippines. *Middle Eastern Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences* 1 (1): 27-34. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/2p82pnv9>
- Asuncion, J. (2019). The Traditional Filipino Games: Status Check among Generation Z. *International Scientific Journal: Theoretical and Applied Science*. Issue 10 Volume 19. Retrieved from <http://tinyurl.com/nhfmpx36>
- Booc, R., Rafaela, K., Torres, M., Bulawan, R., Jabonero II, L., Cortuna, I. J., & Asuncion, J. (2019). The traditional Filipino games: status check among generation Z. *Theoretical & Applied Science* 78 (10): 150-152. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/22sx8f4z>
- Cho, M. (2000). Expanded Awareness Model. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/mrhpkzsw>
- Commission on Higher Education. (2017). CHED Memorandum Order No. 80- Policies, Standards and Guidelines for Bachelor of Physical Education (BPEd). Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/2p8z9kpy>
- Dehorkdi, M. R. (2017). The Educational Impact of Traditional Games: the Role of Zurkhaneh Sport in Educating Children. Volume 5, Issue 3, 134- 139. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/hky39hnx>
- De La Cruz, C. I. (2018). We May Soon Have National Competitions for Filipino Games. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/2p88um6u>
- Elger, D. (2007) *Theory of Performance*. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/3nhu6k5m>
- Eslit, N. (2019). Traditional Filipino Games Series #04: Kadang-Kadang. Retrieved from website <https://tinyurl.com/yv5ehj5b>
- Eslit, N. (2019). Traditional Filipino Games Series #03: Luksong Baka – The Catalyst. Retrieved from website <https://tinyurl.com/2p8ubyzb>
- Larong Pilipinas. Mga Laro at Batas. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/4rpsthrk>
- Lopez, M. (1980). *A Study of Philippine Games*. University of the Philippines Press. Page 431-432.
- Morales, M. P. E. (2016). Exploring Indigenous Game-based Physics Activities in Pre-Service Physics Teachers' Conceptual Change and Transformation of Epistemic Beliefs. (PDF document). Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/3uwrzfp4>
- Mozar, J. R. (2020). Enhance Curriculum with the Integration of Indigenous Game to Physical Education in the different State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) in CARAGA Region, Philippines. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/3cs54fdr>
- Noor, W. M., Razak, R. F. H. A., & Ahmad, M. A. (2019). "TRADSIX"- Selected Traditional Games In A Box: A New Approach in Raising Awareness and Interest On Traditional Games Towards Children. (PDF document). Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/2p8kv96b>
- Popeska, B., & Jovanova Mitkovska, S. (2017). TRADITIONAL GAMES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL CURRICULUM. KNOWLEDGE – *International Journal*, 16(4), 1541-1548. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/63sfnu23>
- Tatli, Z. (2018). Traditional and Digital Game Preferences of Children: A CHAID Analysis on Middle School Students. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/324x4747>
- The 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines. (n.d). Article XIV Section 19. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/257pesxx>
- Thesis Blog of Team 13. (2013 January 17). Review of Related Literature and Studies. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/2km43rk8>

Valamis (2022). Learning Curve Theory. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/45nd8tk5>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Marisol E. Coyoca

Holy Name University – Philippines

Mary Nicolette D. Sulague

Holy Name University – Philippines

Paolo Javier Requilme

Holy Name University – Philippines

Jann Bryle T. Unajan

Holy Name University – Philippines

Rafunzel Y. Bulilawa

Holy Name University – Philippines

Edsel Barnette S. Tatad

Holy Name University – Philippines